

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL APPS IN TEACHING LANGUAGES

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Abstract In this article, it is aimed to explore the role of educational apps in teaching languages. Besides that, advantage and disadvantages of educational apps are discussed and concluded that educational apps made education mobile, portable, convenient and fun.

Key words: educational app, online learning, e-learning, technological devices, mobility, portability, higher engagement.

Introduction

In the 21st century, technological era, we cannot image our life without technological devices. Like other spheres, education also experienced the accomplishments of IT gadgets. Obviously, dramatic increase of technological gadgets created new notions of education, such as mobile-learning. When we talk about technology and mobile apps, they have also revolutionized the teaching and learning field (take the Duolingo – a language learning app, for example). These informatics technologies inspire language learners, assist language teachers to apply them effortlessly.

One of the main factors of language learning app development was Covid-19 virus. Because of quarantine classrooms shifted online one. Most learners and educators discovered a number of convenience and benefits of online learning, Classes, lectures, and seminars are no longer confined to the classrooms only. Students are gravitating from paperback to digital books, preferring online classes more often than offline ones, completing various courses digitally; thus, reshaping the education industry.

It is clear how important educational apps and e-learning are in modern education system. As a coin has two sides, educational apps also have advantages and disadvantages. We are going to illustrate some of them.

Advantages:

1. Mobility and portability. There are no special requirements of educational apps and online learning. There is no need for special place and educational schedule, besides that commuting to study. Furthermore, learners can learn just with the help of their smart technological devices, for instance smart phones, tablets, laptops and computers. They create convenient environment for both learners and teachers.

2. Higher Engagement. Visual aids always appeal learners a bit more than textual messages or written information. Educational apps contain a number of visuals: photos, videos, graphic organizers and motions. It becomes difficult for students to stay focused in the classrooms because classroom studies are a bit mundane. On the other hand, educational apps are stimulating and fun to use; thus, attracting many learners.

3. Personalized and Interactive Learning. Personalization is one of the key advantages of educational apps. Personalization is one of the most interactive learning ways, encouraging learners to engage with the app more and more. Educational apps are becoming the new priority choice for learners as they allow them to learn anything in their comfort, at their own pace.

4. Effortless Teaching. An educational app minimizes teachers' efforts. There is no need for teachers to worry about learners' attendance and attention as educational apps offer highly appealing and engaging UI for learners to interact with their devices. Also, learners can get the entire module on mobile phones, ensuring timely syllabus completion. Hence, improving results amongst students.

5. Online Study Material. Online tutorials and e-books have made students' life easier and hassle-free. With the advancement of technology, learners can access

a variety of books with a mere click. If students have an educational app on their mobile phones, it means they have all the books that can fit right into their pockets easily. That said, learners don't need to buy books and study material as they can easily find all the books online.

6. 24/7 Availability. Unlike schools and colleges, educational mobile apps are available 24/7. Therefore, there's no such thing as time-bound learning. Educational apps work the best regarding this issue and let learners learn new things at their convenience with round-the-clock availability. Plus, the educational app can help students clear their doubts anytime and anywhere.

Although there are several advantages of educational apps, disadvantages of them can be found. For example,

1. Lack of Real Interaction. Because of lack of real interaction learners can lose their public speaking and also they may face difficulties in social communications.

2. Distraction. One of the most striking disadvantages of the educational app is it leads to distraction from other lessons. It is easy to be disturbed by internet advertisements, social networks or other entertainments.

3. Internet Connection. Even if we are living in modern world there are plenty of areas where internet connection is problematic. Moreover, there are other negative aspect of educational apps, such as out of internet pack, data, low batteries and other technological disorders.

It is obvious that advantages of educational apps overweight disadvantages of them. And of course, it depends on learner`s goals aimed to achieve.

Conclusion

Using educational apps is a double-edged sword as it has several advantages but multiple shortcomings as well. However, the world is advancing with the advent of technology; therefore, developing a learning app (keeping the importance of

educational apps in mind) can be a smart move to attract more learners and make education efficient.

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